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ABSTRACT

The EJP Soil EnergyLink project aims for a better understanding of the link between crop diversification and carbon sequestration via the soil microbiome. This document reports on the synthesized results of the project. It provides answers to the aspects of the projects main hypothesis that aboveground plant diversity produces soil organic matter (SOM) with greater molecular diversity, which in turn affects the return on metabolic investment (ROI) and microbial carbon use efficiency (CUE) of the soil microbiome, resulting in a larger C sequestration potential in soil.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

WP	work package
C	carbon
CUE	carbon use efficiency
LTE	long-term experimental site
MAP	mean annual precipitation
MAT	mean annual temperature
NMR	nuclear magnetic resonance
ROI	energetic return on metabolic investment
SOC	soil organic carbon
SOM	soil organic matter

1. Introduction

The EnergyLink project aimed to improve our understanding on how aboveground plant trait diversity can be used to manage belowground carbon use efficiency (CUE) of the soil microbiome and organic matter persistence in soil. The over-arching premise was that aboveground plant trait diversity can be exploited to manage microbial functional diversity and carbon use efficiency in soils, thus optimizing carbon (C) dynamics and improving the ecosystem services of C sequestration and global change mitigation.

The project was constructed around the central hypothesis that aboveground plant diversity produces soil organic matter (SOM) with greater molecular diversity (Fig. 1). This in turn, affects the return on metabolic investment (ROI) and microbial CUE, resulting in a larger C sequestration potential in soil (Fig. 1). An ancillary hypothesis was that the relationship between microbial CUE and organic matter inputs is modulated by the functional diversity and composition of the soil microbiome.

Figure 1. Conceptual bioenergetics framework: Hypothetical relation between plant diversification, return on metabolic investment, microbial carbon use efficiency and C sequestration potential in soil.

Microbial CUE is considered a key control factor on the fate of organic C in soil (Fig. 2). It determines the proportion of metabolised C allocated towards microbial biomass formation in contrast to respiratory CO₂ emission during microbial breakdown of SOM (Bölscher et al., 2020; Manzoni et al. 2012; Schroeder et al., 2024). Biomass formation provides a potential for the accumulation of necromass in soils, which is considered a major fraction of SOM (Liang et al., 2017; Liang et al., 2019). Owing to its crucial role in terrestrial-C dynamics, small changes in CUE may have major implications for soil-C storage (Bölscher et al., 2020). The energetic ROI is a rather novel parameter proposed to differentiate short-to-medium term biodegradability of SOM (Harvey et al., 2016). The ROI is the ratio between the total net energy available and the

activation energy required to completely oxidize organic matter under aerobic conditions. The activation energy causes an energetic barrier for microbial decomposition (Fig. 2; Dufour et al., 2022; Williams et al., 2018).

Figure 2. Schematic illustration of the energetic return on metabolic investment (ROI) and microbial carbon use efficiency (CUE) during decomposition of soil organic carbon (C).

2. Field sites

Eight agricultural long-term experimental sites (LTE) along a pan-European pedo-climatic gradient were selected for the EnergyLink project, representing crop diversification across Europe (Fig. 3; see deliverable D2.1). Each LTE had at least one diversified treatment representing crop diversification practices typical in the respective region, as well as a non-diversified control. Mean annual temperature (MAT) and precipitation (MAP) ranged from 8.9 °C to 18.5 °C and 578 mm to 1529 mm, respectively, while vegetation length varied between 365 and 218 days per year (Table 1). The investigated crop diversification measures included i) cover crops, ii) introduction of temporal grassland in annual crop rotations (hereafter referred to as ley farming), and iii) vegetation stripes between perennial crops (Fig. 3).

To cover the temporal dimension of crop diversification, bulk topsoil samples (0-20 cm) were taken twice during the vegetation period at the sites in Sweden, Spain, France, Slovenia and three times in the Netherlands. No second sampling was possible at the sites in Lithuania, the Czech Republic and Austria (see deliverable D2.2).

Figure 3. Selected long-term experimental sites (LTE) for the EnergyLink project are located along a pan-European pedo-climatic gradient covering different diversification measures, i.e. cover crops (violet), ley farming (green), and vegetation stripes (yellow).

Table 1. Location, climate data and treatments of the long-term experimental sites (LTE). Climate data source: CHELSA Bioclim (Karger et al., 2017; Karger et al., 2018). MAT = mean annual temperature, MAP = mean annual precipitation, C = control, T1 and T3 = plant diversification treatments.

Country	LTE	EPSG 4326		MAT	MAP	Growing season	Köppen Geiger	Treatment
		latitude	longitude	°C	mm	days		
Sweden ¹	Mellby R0-8403	55.496	13.04	7.7	925	242	19	C: spring grain dominated crop rotation without catch crop T3: spring grain dominated crop rotation with ryegrass
Lithuania	Dotnuva LAMMC cover crops	55.413	23.864	7.2	615	218	19	C: control bare soil T1: mustard T3: phacelia
Netherlands ²	Wageningen Clever Cover Cropping	51.995	55.659	10.2	888	365	10	Main crop rotation: wheat-maize (2022)-potato-barley-pea-barley C: crop rotation without cover crop T3: crop rotation with cover crops (vetch, oats, radish)
Czech Republic ³	Prague Ruzyně	50.085	14.301	8.9	578	269	19	Spring barley followed by different cover crops C: spring barley without cover crops T1: spring barley with cover crop sinapis alba T3: spring barley with cover crop sinapis alba plus fagopyrum
Austria	St. Florian	48.212	14.383	9.8	856	280	19	C: fallow T1: white lupin T3: aqua pro mix: phacelia, linseed, sunflower, bristle oat, niger, sorghum, safflower
France ⁴	Lusignan	46.413	0.12	11.9	878	365	10	C: maize, wheat, barley since 2005 T1: 3-year grassland followed by 3 crop sequences T3: permanent grassland since 2005
Slovenia	Vineyards Koper	45.5*	13.7*	14.3	1529	365	9	Vineyard with different interrow management since 1997: C: bare soil with tillage to control weeds in interrow T3: permanent natural vegetation cover
Spain	Seville Benacazón	37.343	-6.229	18.5	600	256	12	C: olive orchard with surface tillage as interrow management T3: olive orchard with mixed natural cover

¹ Aronsson and Torstensson, 1998; Poeplau et al., 2015; ² Elhakeem et al., 2023; ³ Hakl et al., 2021; ⁴ Hu and Chabbi, 2022

3. Synthesis

In the following section, we will present our synthesized results, providing answers to each specific aspect of the main research hypothesis that aboveground plant diversity produces SOM with greater molecular diversity which in turn affects the ROI and microbial CUE, resulting in a larger C sequestration potential in soil (Fig. 1). In addition, we answer the ancillary hypothesis that the relationship between microbial CUE and organic matter inputs is modulated by the functional diversity and composition of the soil microbiome

3.1. Plant diversification resulting in a larger C sequestration potential in soil

Overall, we found no effect of plant diversification on soil organic carbon (SOC) content, and thus no clear evidence for increased C sequestration potential, in the eight investigated LTEs (Fig. 4, see also deliverable D5.2). However, separating the results by plant diversification practices (i.e. cover crops, ley farming and vegetation stripes) revealed that introduction of vegetation stripes between perennial crops increased SOC content compared to sites with bare stripes between perennial crops (Fig. 4). For cover crop and ley farming, diversification did not lead to increased SOC (Fig. 4). In summary, only the introduction of vegetation stripes between perennial crops at LTE in Slovenia and Spain increased SOC, while cover crops and ley farming had no effect on SOC. Consequently, plant diversification only resulted in larger C sequestration potential for the introduction of vegetation stripes.

Figure 4. Overall and diversification measure-specific effect sizes of crop diversification on soil organic carbon (SOC). Effects of plant diversification are shown as response ratio (RR), i.e. relative change diversified versus control treatment. Coloured circles mark single observations, where the size represents its weighted contribution to the estimated overall effect. Asterisks indicate significant diversification effects (***) $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$).

3.2. Aboveground plant diversity produces SOM with greater molecular diversity

We found only limited evidence for greater molecular diversity of SOM, analysed by solid state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), after the introduction of plant diversification measures (Fig. 5; see also deliverable D3.1). Only SOM at the Slovenian LTE (i.e. vegetation stripes between perennial crops) revealed significant effects of plant diversification on its molecular composition which were consistent over time (i.e. consistently present in samples taken in spring and autumn). Here, especially the ratio of alkyl-to-oxygen-alkyl functional C groups decreased with the plant diversification treatment, indicating a lower humification index for SOM in the diversification treatment (Fig. 5). Additional differences in molecular diversity were found in the samples from the Dutch, Swedish, French and Czech LTEs, but these differences were not consistent over time (Fig. 5). Clear indication for plant diversification affecting molecular diversity of SOM were thus only revealed for one of the two LTEs with introduction of vegetation stripes between perennial plants which also had higher SOC content (Fig. 4).

Figure 5. Functional carbon (C) groups of soil organic matter (SOM) analysed by solid state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) in soil samples from seven long-term experimental sites (LTEs). Graphs show mean values with standard errors (***) $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$. C = control, T1 and T3 = plant diversification treatments, see table 1 for details on control and treatments T1 and T3.

3.3. Plant diversification and greater molecular diversity of SOM affects the ROI and CUE of the soil microbiome

The potential energetic ROI (Dufour et al., 2022) could not be investigated as planned due to limited size of soil samples from the eight investigated LTEs (see deliverable D3.3)

Overall, microbial CUE in bulk soil was not affected by plant diversification (Fig. 6). This is because plant diversification induced by tendency similar increases in microbial growth and respiration, although these changes were overall not significant (Fig. 6). Plant diversification did thus not trigger overall major shifts in microbial metabolism (at least in bulk soil, rhizosphere soil was not investigated separately).

Introduction of ley farming (i.e. French LTE) did, however, increase microbial CUE and microbial necromass contribution to SOC significantly (Fig. 6 and 7, respectively). The latter may not be caused by increased CUE alone, but also by faster microbial turnover rates (Fig. 8). Despite these changes, total SOC remained unaffected (see 3.1., Fig. 4). The introduction of vegetation stripes between perennial crops (i.e. Slovenian and Spanish LTEs) increased microbial growth, respiration and biomass (Fig. 6), but microbial CUE remained unchanged because growth and respiration increased to similar degrees (Fig. 6). This increased microbial growth was solely caused by higher bacterial growth rates, while fungal growth rates decreased (Fig. 8). The introduction of vegetation stripes also tended to increase the contribution of microbial necromass to SOC (Fig. 7), likely derived by faster fungal, and for Slovenia bacterial, turnover rates (Fig. 8). Together, these changes may have contributed to the increased SOC in vegetation stripe fields (see 3.1, Fig. 4). Although showing no differences in microbial CUE, introduction of cover crops at the Austrian LTE caused faster fungal and bacterial turnover (Fig. 8) which lead to a higher necromass contribution to SOC (by tendency; Fig. 7).

Figure 6. Overall and diversification measure-specific effect sizes of plant diversification on microbial carbon use efficiency (CUE), growth (C_{Growth}), respiration ($C_{Respiration}$), and biomass C (C_{mic}). Effects of crop diversification are shown as response ratio (RR), i.e. relative change diversified versus control treatment. Coloured circles mark single observations, where the size represents its weighted contribution to the estimated overall effect. Asterisks indicate significant diversification effects (*** $p < 0.001$, ** $p < 0.01$, * $p < 0.05$).

Figure 7. Contribution of microbial necromass to soil organic carbon (SOC) measured in soil samples six long-term experimental sites (LTE).

Figure 8. a) Bacterial and b) fungal growth rates as well as c) bacterial and d) fungal turnover rates measured in soil samples of six long-term experimental sites. Results are shown for plant diversification treatments expressed as percent relative to control treatments indicated by the red dotted 100 % line.

3.4. The relationship between CUE and organic matter inputs is modulated by the diversity of the soil microbiome

Part of the project's hypothesis is that crop diversification will increase microbial diversity which again will lead to an increase in microbial CUE. To test these parts of the main hypothesis, we analysed soil samples regarding the composition of the microbial communities and their functional diversity.

3.4.1. Does plant diversification affect the richness of soil microbial communities?

The diversity of microbial communities was analysed by amplicon sequencing of the 16S (bacterial) and ITS (fungi) fragments on surface soil (0-20 cm; see Deliverable 4.1) samples from the LTEs in Austria, France, the Netherlands, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden (see Table 1). Overall, we observed that bacterial richness was not affected by crop diversification, while fungal richness (i.e., number of observed amplicon sequence variants) increased with crop diversification (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Microbial diversity shown as richness of bacteria and fungi, comparing control to the plant diversification treatments.

When microbial diversity was investigated for single LTEs, no differences in bacterial richness were found at all sites, while fungal richness revealed no consistent pattern (Fig. 10). Statistically significant higher fungal richness in plant diversity treatments was only found at the Slovenian site (i.e. vineyard with interrow vegetation stripes; Fig. 10). Trends towards higher bacterial richness with plant diversification may also be present at some of the other field sites. In addition, the fungal composition was also affected by sites while bacterial composition was not. Overall, our findings demonstrate that effects of plant diversification on microbial diversity in soils is context-dependent (e.g. pedo-climatic conditions) and affect microbial groups differently.

Figure 10. Richness of bacteria (left) and fungi (right) separated by LTE, comparing control and diversification treatments.

3.4.2. Does plant diversification affect the microbial functional diversity?

We used multiple substrate-induced respiration (MicroResp approach; Campbell et al., 2003) to evaluate the functional diversity status of the soil microbiome. Initially, it was planned to use this approach on soils from all eight LTE, but soils from Czech Republic, Slovenia and Spain contained carbonates which hamper a reliable application of the method. Principal component analysis of MicroResp data revealed that plant diversification separated microbial functional diversity between diversified soils compared to controls only at the Swedish LTE (Fig. 11; see also deliverable D4.3).

Figure 11. Microbial functional diversity analysed using the MicroResp approach. Graphs show results investigated by principle component analysis. (A) Functional diversity profiles separated by LTE. (B) Differentiation between control and plant diversification treatments for each LTE, revealing a clear separation only at the Swedish LTE. Blue points are control (C) treatments and other colours indicate plant diversification treatments (T1, T3). (C) Circle of correlation with the weight of each substrate in the separation of samples.

3.5. Synthesis summary

In summary, we have to reject our project hypotheses that (i) aboveground plant diversity produces SOM with greater molecular diversity which, in turn, affects microbial CUE resulting in a larger C sequestration potential in soil as well as that (ii) the relationship between CUE and organic matter inputs is modulated by the functional and compositional diversity of the soil microbiome. Overall, plant diversification had no effect on C sequestration potentials, molecular diversity of SOM, or microbial CUE in bulk soil. In addition, overall a higher plant diversity did also not increase the microbial functional diversity and microbial composition. Thus, a modulation between CUE and organic matter inputs was also not modulated by microbial functional or compositional diversity.

Significant increases in C sequestration potential, molecular SOM diversity and fungal richness were only discovered for introduction of vegetation stripes between perennial plants. These changes had however no effect on microbial CUE, because microbial growth and respiration increased with similar degrees. It remains unclear if the changes in growth and respiration were solely triggered by larger C inputs or were also affected by SOM molecular diversity.

We investigated bulk soil samples, because we considered bulk soil as the important level for soil C storage. We cannot rule out that some of the investigated processes may be relevant in soil close to plant roots.

4. Outlook

Although we observed only few changes in microbial CUE with plant diversification (i.e. for ley farming, Fig. 4), we cannot rule out that microbial pathways contributing to SOC stabilization may have changed in most soils after the introduction of plant diversification measures. We found, for example, higher microbial growth, respiration and biomass in soil with vegetation stripes between perennial crops (Fig. 6), which aligned with changes in specific fungal and bacterial growth rates, turnover (Fig. 7), contribution of microbial necromass to SOC (Fig. 8) and fungal diversity (Fig. 10). These changes may have been triggered by higher C inputs, especially by roots, and point towards the importance of root exudates to the so called in-vivo pathway of SOM stabilization (Liang et al., 2017). Similar changes together with increased microbial CUE after the introduction of ley-farming (i.e. French LTE; Fig. 4, 6-8) support this notion. Taken our observations together, the results of this project may suggest that microbial CUE is not as important factor in the 'microbial carbon pump' (Liang et al., 2017) as often assumed. Instead, fast-growing microbial communities with high biomass turnover rates may be an important factor in the microbial SOC stabilization pathways. Such microbial communities can trigger a large contribution of microbial necromass to SOC and may be fuelled through inputs of easily available substrates close to roots. Plant diversification measures with increase root biomass over extended periods of time, such as vegetation trips or ley farming, may thus lead to higher growth and turnover of microbial biomass per added C to the soil, increasing the relative importance of the microbial SOC stabilization pathway. This idea, that not microbial CUE, but microbial growth, biomass and turnover may be most important for the microbial pathway of C stabilization in soils should be followed-up in future research. Following our thoughts, we have therefore planned to perform SOM fractionation on stored samples from this project to analyse potential changes in the mineral-associated organic carbon fraction. This SOM fraction is considered to be most stable and largely derived from microbial necromass (Liang et al., 2017; Lavalley et al., 2020). The planned analysis may thus shed additional light on whether faster growth and turnover and more necromass-C in vegetation stripes contributed to more stable and more total SOC.

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